

Comparative transmission of two RTSV strains.

IRGC ¹ Acc. no.	Variety name	RTSV infection (%)		IRGC ² Acc. no.	Variety name	RTSV infection (%)	
		Strain A	Strain Vt6			Strain A	Strain Vt6
177	Adday Sel.	0	0	27779	Bara Pashawari	390	0
180	Adday Local Sel.	0	0	27787	Basmati Nahani	381	13
237	TKM6	0	59	27798	Basmati 1	10	100
10262	G378	0	100	27818	Basmati 242	0	29
11751	Habiganj DW8	0	26	27829	Basmati 377	3	82
12274	ARC6561	7	100	27830	Basmati 388	11	94
12428	ARC10312	0	93	27832	Basmati 405	0	97
12437	ARC10343	0	78	27833	Basmati 406	0	13
12765	Kataribhog	5	74	27836	Basmati 433	0	98
14504	IR580 420-1-1-2	4	58	27856	Begumi 302	10	18
14527	Barah	0	41	27869	Chahora 144	3	100
16680	Utri Merah	0	3	27870	Chahora 148	0	83
16684	Utri Rajapan	38	79	27872	Chahora 292	0	97
19680	ARC10963	0	68	27873	Chahora 382	0	100
20600	ARC7321	0	18	27946	Hansraj 62	0	100
21310	ARC11315	0	80	27947	Hansraj 189	0	100
21474	ARC11555	0	14	27951	Hansraj 365A	0	92
21745	ARC11920	0	8	28102	P590	0	92
21958	ARC12170	3	94	28522	Gundrikbhog	0	50
22199	ARC12620	0	51	28867	Aus 4	0	100
22215	ARC12636	0	15	36731	Firro E(1)	0	16
22307	ARC12746	0	52	37215	Matichakma	0	67
22331	ARC12778	0	28	37337	Urman Sardar	0	51
26253	Nep Bap	0	8	37482	Konekchul	0	92
26410	Pala Bhir	3	3	37761	Maliabhangor	1096	3
26495	Konek Chul	3	8	49996	Ovarikondoh	0	3
26527	Shull 2	0	86	11355	IR20 ^b	0	16
26582	Buchi 2	0	100	24153	IR26 ^b	0	8
26791	Sham Rosh	0	3	30413	IR30 ^b	0	6
26813	Gogoj	0	3	21473	ARC11554 ^b	0	0
105	Taichung Native 1	98	95				

¹IRGC = International Rice Germplasm Center. ²Vector-resistant variety. Other varieties are susceptible to GLH after IRR1 data base on GLH resistance.

of resistance genes to both strains of RTSV. Information on the occurrence of virus strains in different regions is needed

for effective deployment of resistance genes. ■

Symptomatic strains of rice tungro bacilliform virus

P. Q. Cabauatan and H. Koganezawa, IRRI

Several tungro virus strains have been reported previously. Most of these reports, however, were published long before the discovery that two viruses are involved in the disease. Hence, the reported strains could be interpreted as being due to either infection with one or both viruses. From an isolate maintained in a greenhouse, we isolated four rice

tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) strains by separating them from rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV). Differential cultivars, TN1 and FK135, were serially inoculated with the strains, using *Nephotettix virescens*, until consistent symptoms were obtained.

The RTBV strains (Ic, G1, and G2) were differentiated from the type strain (L) by the symptoms they cause on FK135 and TN1. On FK135, strain Ic induced distinct interveinal chlorosis, stunting, reduced tillering, and narrow leaves, whereas G1 and G2 caused only

mild stunting, with foliage remaining normal and green. Symptoms caused by these strains were milder than those caused by strain L, which induces very severe stunting and interveinal chlorosis (Fig. 1a). On TN1, Ic and G1 caused mild stunting and foliage remained green in contrast with G2, which caused severe stunting and discoloration similar to the type strain (Fig. 1b).

Cross-inoculation experiments showed that strains G1 and Ic were cross-protective. FK135 plants infected with G1 did not show changes in symptom pattern when challenge-inoculated with Ic 1 or 2 wk after inoculation with G1, and vice versa. When virus-free green leafhoppers were allowed to access cross-inoculated plants for 24 h and used to inoculate FK135 seedlings, only the strain inoculated first was transmitted. Cross protection was incomplete when challenge inoculation was done at a 1-d interval. Most of the inoculated plants, however, showed the symptoms of the strain inoculated first. Both strains were recovered from these plants, but more of the strain inoculated first (see table).

These results indicate that RTBV is variable. The difference in symptom expression of the strains on TN1 and FK135 indicated that at least two viral

Cross-inoculation between RTBV strains G1 and Ic at different time intervals and virus recovery from cross-inoculated plants 1 mo after the second inoculation.

Interval between inoculations	Inoculation sequence ^a	Plants (no.) with symptoms ^b of		Strains re-covered ^c (no.)	
		1st	2d	1st	2d
2 wk	G1 Ic	19	0	94	0
	Ic G1	17	0	69	0
1 wk	G1 Ic	33	0	129	0
	Ic G1	17	0	88	0
1 d	G1 Ic	46	5	120	38
	Ic G1	39	4	111	14
Control	G1 None	17	0	30	0
	Ic None	17	0	61	0

^aFive viruliferous leafhoppers were confined with 2-wk-old FK135 plants for 24-h inoculation access. ^bBased on presence or absence of interveinal chlorosis 1 mo after the second inoculation. ^cVirus-free leafhoppers were allowed 24 h access to cross-inoculated plants showing symptoms of the 1st virus and used to inoculate 6-d-old FK135 seedlings. Plants were scored 1 mo after inoculation.

Symptoms exhibited by RTBV strains on rice cultivars FK135 (a) and TN1. (b) Left to right: healthy plants (check) and plants infected with strains Ic, G1, G2, and L.

genes (one for TN1 and another for FK135) are involved in RTBV symptom expression. RTBV strains could be used for comparative studies on the mechanisms of pathogenicity of the virus. ■

Inheritance of resistance to rice blast disease in some japonicas

Shi Chunhai, Agronomy Department, Zhejiang Agricultural University, Hangzhou 310029; and Shi De, Sun Guocang, Tao Rongxiang, and Sun Shuyuan, Institute of Plant Protection, Zhejiang Agricultural Academy, Hangzhou 310021, China

Rice blast (BI) disease (*Magnaporthe grisea* [Hebert] Barr) is a major constraint to rice production in China. Crosses of the susceptible variety, Nongfu 6 (NF6), and five resistant varieties, Xianghu 84 (XU84, derived from C81-45//Ce 21/Xianghu 14), Xianghu 25 (XU25, derived from Aijing 23/Xianghu 14//Ce 21/Aijing 23), Xiushui 04 (XS04, derived from

Table 1. F₂ segregation of S/R^a crosses with resistance to the 3 rice BI races.^b

Race	Cross	Reaction (no.)							χ^2	
		Parents		F ₁		F ₂			3:1	15:1
		R	S	R	S	R	M	S		
ZB ₁₃	NF6/XH84	9	0	9	0	296	1	19	0.1949	0.0034
	NF6/XU25	26	0	10	0	305	4	16		0.7633
	NF6/XS04	13	0	11	0	528	2	33		0.0863
	NF6/XS11	9	0	11	0	213	0	76		
	NF6/XS24	9	0	11	0	442	3	26		
	NF6	0	10							
ZC ₁₅	NF6/XH84	9	0	9	0	261	2	16	0.0048	0.0538
	NF6/XU25	21	0	10	0	279	3	16		0.2586
	NF6/XS04	18	0	11	0	415	0	26		0.0437
	NF6/XS11	8	0	11	0	204	4	68		
	NF6/XS24	11	0	11	0	449	0	27		0.1815
	NF6	0	10							
ZE ₃	NF6/XH84	9	0	9	0	284	2	17	2.3050	0.1164
	NF6/XU25	17	0	10	0	275	0	18		0.0021
	NF6/XS04	18	0	11	0	453	6	26		0.5115
	NF6/XS11	9	0	11	0	242	7	67		
	NF6/XS24	15	0	11	0	321	1	20		0.0382
	NF6	0	10							

^aR = resistant, M = moderately resistant, and S = susceptible. ^b5% significance level, $\chi^2 = 3.84$.

Table 2. F₂ segregation of R/R crosses with resistance to the 3 rice BI races.^a

Race	Cross	Reaction (no.)					χ^2	
		F ₁		F ₂			63:1	255:1
		R	S	R	M	S		
ZB ₁₃	XU84/XU25	10	0	523	0	2	0.0001	0.0988
	XU84/XS04	17	0	531	0	2		0.0842
	XU84/XS11	12	0	469	1	8		0.0040
	XU84/XS24	18	0	612	0	3		0.0501
	XU25/XS04	16	0	735	0	2		
	XU25/XS11	18	0	927	0	0		
	XU25/XS24	15	0	461	0	0		
	XS04/XS11	11	0	461	0	7		0.0049
	XS04/XS24	10	0	569	0	2		0.0328
	XS11/XS24	13	0	562	1	8		0.0203
ZC ₁₅	XU84/XU25	10	0	666	1	2	0.4750	0.0049
	XU84/XS04	17	0	528	0	2		0.0895
	XU84/XS11	12	0	392	1	4		
	XU84/XS24	18	0	563	0	0		
	XU25/XS04	16	0	756	0	0		
	XU25/XS11	18	0	684	0	0		
	XU25/XS24	15	0	507	0	0		
	XS04/XS11	11	0	512	0	0		
	XS04/XS24	10	0	518	0	0		
	XS11/XS24	13	0	489	0	0		
ZE ₃	XU84/XU25	10	0	391	0	0	0.0161	
	XU84/XS04	17	0	548	0	0		0.0026
	XU84/XS11	12	0	481	0	8		0.1029
	XU84/XS24	18	0	518	0	2		
	XU25/XS04	16	0	848	0	0		
	XU25/XS11	18	0	907	0	13		0.0541
	XU25/XS24	15	0	604	0	0		
	XS04/XS11	11	0	880	0	14		
	XS04/XS24	10	0	584	1	1		0.2731
	XS11/XS24	13	0	518	0	0		

^a5% significance level, $\chi^2 = 3.84$.